

2-o-Tolylureide of 3-Aminophenazine.

The precipitate, which separated on adding water containing a little common salt to the solution obtained by boiling 1 gm. of 2:3-diaminophenazine and 1.5 gms. of *o*-tolyl mustard oil in 50 c.c. of glacial acetic acid for half an hour, crystallised from alcohol in violet needles, not melting below 300°.

It is soluble in alcohol, hot water or dilute hydrochloric acid. It gives a green colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found : N = 19.91. $C_{20}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N = 19.47 per cent.).

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Dithiocatechol.

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Although dithiocatechol has been described (Pollak, *Monatsh.*, 1918, 34, 1673), its activity towards ring-closing agents has not been recorded. The present work was undertaken with a view to synthesise various ring compounds of sulphur derived from dithiocatechol. Dithiocatechol was originally obtained by Pollak (*loc. cit.*) by the reduction of benzene *o*-disulphonic acid. We

have, however, prepared the mercaptan by three different methods outlined below.

(i) 2-Xantho-5-bromo-potassium benzene sulphonate (I) is prepared from acetanilide according to the method of Armstrong and Napper (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 16, 160), hydrolysed to the dipotassium salt of 5-bromo-2-thiol-benzene sulphonic acid (II), oxidised to 5:5'-dibromo 1:1'-disulpho-diphenyl-2:2'-disulphide (III)—this step is necessary as otherwise the free mercaptanic group would interfere with the formation of the sulphochloride in the next step—which yields the corresponding disulphochloride of dibromodiphenyl disulphide (IV), which, subjected to the reducing action of tin and hydrochloric acid, yields two molecules of 1-bromo-3:4-dithiocatechol (V), and this bromo-mercaptan is finally debrominated by the action of zinc dust and alkali to the alkali salt of dithiocatechol, from which acid liberates the free dimercaptan (VI).

(ii) The second method consists in treating the xanthate compound (I) with potassium permanganate when the xanthate portion is oxidised to a sulphonic acid group giving rise to bromobenzene-*o*-disulphonic acid (VII), which is debrominated to yield the potassium salt of benzene-*o*-disulphonic acid (VIII), the chloride (IX) of which is finally reduced to dithiocatechol. A red solid is formed as an intermediate product which is further

reduced with difficulty and is supposed from its properties to be the lactone* of 1-thiol-2-sulphonic acid of benzene, the formation of which proves that the reduction proceeds step by step.

The production of this stable substance was really puzzling and more than once led the present authors to believe that dithiocatechol could not be prepared by this method.

(iii) Sulphur has long been employed for the preparation of the aromatic mercaptans (Friedel and Crafts, *Compt. rend.*, 86, 884; Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2807; Hinsberg, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1337; Hatinger, *Monat.*, 1883, 4, 165). In the present instance, it has been found that by heating together sodium-thiophenate and sulphur at high temperatures, a mixture of several compounds (sulphides, disulphides, etc.) is formed from which dithiocatechol can be obtained by reduction and fractional distillation.

Of the above three methods, the first and the second are decidedly superior to the third one. The success of the first method mainly depends upon the step by which the compound (I) is hydrolysed to the compound (II). It should also be mentioned here that the isolation of dithiocatechol from the mixture obtained in method (iii) would not have been possible but for the knowledge about its nature and physical properties previously

* The supposed thiolactone is under investigation.

gathered from a pure sample prepared by other methods.

Besides preparing a dibenzoyl derivative and a disulphide of dithiocatechol, it has been condensed with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and acenaphthaquinone. One molecule of the nitrobenzaldehyde reacts with one molecule of the dimercaptan, thus,

In the case of acenaphthaquinone, only one ketonic group reacts with one molecule of the dimercaptan to give a mono-mercaptol:

It was anticipated that chlorocarbonic ester would react with the dimercaptan to give either a dicarbethoxy compound $Br.C_6H_4(SCOOEt)_2$ or a thiocarbonate $Br.C_6H_4:S_2:CO$ as has been observed in the case of catechol, but it has been found in actual practice that the expected dicarbethoxy compound first formed loses two molecules of carbon dioxide to give rise to a diethyl thioether, thus:

A similar phenomenon was observed by Dixon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 550) and by Wilson and Burns (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 122, 872). That the compound so formed in this reaction is really a diethyl-thiol derivative has been easily proved by preparing the same compound by the action of ethyl bromide on the dimercaptan.

The potassium salt of bromo-dithiocatechol reacts very readily with potassium monochloroacetate to give the potassium salt of bromophenylene-dithiodiglycollic acid,

from which the free acid is liberated by hydrochloric acid. If, however, the free acid is taken instead of the potassium salt and the mixture heated, the reaction proceeds in an entirely different way and a thio-lactone* is formed thus :

Benzal chloride reacts with the dimercaptan in the ordinary way to give benzylidene-bromodithiocatechol, thus :

The same compound has also been obtained from benzaldehyde and the dimercaptan.

The action of acetylene tetrabromide is interesting as it reacts with two molecules of the mercaptan. The product may be represented by one of the following formulæ :

By analogy with the formula ascribed to the corresponding compound of catechol (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 3, 21, 101, 106), the authors are inclined to give preference to formula (A).

The action of acid chlorides, *viz.*, thionyl chloride and oxalyl chloride has also been studied and compounds quite

* For the analogous compound of catechol, *vide* Ludewig (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1900, 61, 345).

similar to those of catechol (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2752; 1890, 23, 1223) have been obtained :

No compound of catechol with thiophosgene is known, but the expected compound of brom-dithiocatechol is formed thus :

Though catechol gives two anthraquinone dyes, *viz.*, alizarine and hystizarine with phthalic anhydride (Bayer and Caro, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 968), bromo-dithiocatechol reacts with the anhydride in an entirely different fashion due to the high reactivity of the thiol groups, and an alkali-insoluble compound is formed which may be represented by one of the following two formulæ (C) and (D).

As the compound is hydrolysed even on boiling with acetic acid, the authors are inclined to give preference to (D).

One molecule of phenanthraquinone reacts with one molecule of the dimercaptan, when boiled under reflux in alcoholic solution, yielding a monomercaptol :

If, however, the reaction is brought about in a sealed tube in presence of alcoholic hydrochloric acid, the dimercaptol $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8(\text{C} : \text{S}_2 : \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{.Br})_2$ is formed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Bromo-4-xantho-benzene-5-potassium sulphonate (I).

Twenty-five grams of the potassium salt of *p*-bromaniline-*o*-sulphonic acid * prepared according to the method of Caries (*Annalen*, 286, 381) and 4 gms. of potassium nitrite were dissolved in water, cooled to 0° and 7 c. c. of sulphuric acid (1.84) diluted to 150 c.c. very slowly added with constant stirring. Gradually the diazo-anhydride separated out; it was rapidly filtered from the solution and washed with water containing ice until free from acid. It was then intimately mixed with a saturated solution of 15 gms. of potassium ethyl xanthate when there was a spontaneous evolution of nitrogen. In order to complete the reaction, the product was warmed up to 70° for about half an hour, a slightly yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained on cooling. It was crystallised from hot water; yield about 80%.

1-Bromo-4-thiolbenzene-5-potassium sulphonate and its Oxidation to the Disulphide.

Twenty grams of 1-bromo-4-xantho-benzene-5 the potassium sulphonate (I) were gently warmed with potassium hydroxide solution (5 gms. in 200 c.c.) for about an hour when it was hydrolysed to the thiol compound, which was partially transformed by aerial oxidation to the disulphide. Air was passed through the solution for a long time to convert the whole of the thiol compound into the disulphide. The solution was then concentrated and the crystalline mass, which separated out, was filtered off and dried. The free acid and its potassium salt are both very soluble in water.

* No description whatsoever is given in the original paper about the preparation of benzene-*o*-disulphonic acid from *p*-bromacetanilide. The present authors had to overcome all the experimental difficulties and to find out the actual methods and that is why the details of preparation are described in this paper.

4:4'-Dibromo-2:2'-disulphochloride of Diphenyl Disulphide.

Ten grams of the potassium salt of dibromo-diphenyl-disulphide-disulphonic acid were thoroughly dried and intimately mixed with 20 gms. of phosphorus pentachloride and heated on the water-bath for 4 to 5 hours with occasional shaking. The semi-solid mass was then poured on to ice. The separated chloride was filtered off, washed with cold water and crystallised from benzene. The yield was 9 gms.

*Reduction of the above Sulphochloride : Formation of
1-Bromo-3:4-dithiocatechol.*

Ten grams of the above chloride were finely powdered and heated with 40 gms. of tin and an excess of conc. hydrochloric acid. After 5 to 6 hours the whole was converted into an oil which was separated by steam distillation. The oil solidified to a crystalline mass as it dropped into the receiver and was purified by precipitation from an ice-cold alcoholic solution by the addition of ice-cold water. It forms a bright yellow lead mercaptide and a pale yellow mercury mercaptide. Iodine throws down the disulphide as an amorphous precipitate from an alcoholic solution of the substance. It is very soluble in alcohol and ether, and melts at 43-44°. (Found: C=32.49; H=2.37; Br=35.98; S=29.13. $C_6H_4S_2Br$ requires C=32.58; H=2.62; Br=36.24 and S=28.95 per cent.).

*Debromination of the Dimercaptan by Zinc Dust and
Caustic Potash : Formation of free Dithiocatechol.*

Twenty grams of 1-bromo-3:4-dithiocatechol were dissolved in a solution of 5 gms. of caustic potash, and the solution was heated with 4 gms. of zinc dust for 9-10 hours over a free flame. After removing the zinc

by filtration, the solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, when an oil separated out which was extracted with ether, dried over anhydrous potassium sulphate, the ether driven off, and finally the oil was distilled. The distillate, coming over between 235° and 238° , was collected. It was redistilled and the fraction between 238° and 239° was retained. It is a colourless transparent oil possessing a mild smell resembling that of thiophenol. It is very soluble in alcohol and ether. It solidifies at $28-29^{\circ}$. (Found: C=50.29; H=4.63; S=46.10. $C_6H_4S_2$ requires C=50.70; H=4.22; S=45.77 per cent.).

1-Bromobenzene-3 : 4-potassium disulphonate.

Bromo-xantho-benzene potassium sulphate (I) was dissolved in boiling water and a concentrated solution of potassium permanganate was added to the solution until the colour of the permanganate persisted. The separated manganese dioxide was filtered off and the solution on concentration gave white crystals of the potassium salt which were filtered off and dried. The yield was quantitative.

1-Bromobenzene-3 : 4-disulphonyl chloride.

Twenty grams of the potassium salt of bromobenzene-*o*-disulphonic acid were thoroughly dried and intimately mixed with 36 gms. of phosphorus pentachloride and heated on a water-bath for 4 to 5 hours with frequent shaking. The semi-solid mass was then poured on to ice. An oil separated which solidified to a crystalline mass on standing. It was washed with cold water and crystallised from benzene. It melted at 100° and not at 104° or 89° as mentioned in *Annalen*, 198, 28 and *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 16, 160 respectively.

Reduction of the above Compound : Formation of Bromo-dithiocatechol.

To a boiling mixture of 30 gms. of granulated tin and an excess of conc. hydrochloric acid, 10 gms. of the sulphochloride were gradually added. The sulphochloride melted and after three or four hours, the whole set to a solid lump which resisted further reduction even on prolonged heating with tin and hydrochloric acid. The red cake¹ was well ground and again introduced into the reaction vessel. After the heating had continued for 5 to 6 hours more, the whole of the red powder disappeared and an oil separated which assumed a reddish tint on cooling, but on being heated again with tin and hydrochloric acid became colourless. The separated oil was distilled with steam and collected in an ice-cold flask where it solidified. The crystalline mass was rapidly filtered off, dissolved in ice-cold alcohol and precipitated with ice-cold water. Its properties are identical with those of bromo-dithiocatechol prepared by the previous method. The yield was 4 gms. (Found : C=32·27; H=2·51. $C_6H_5S_2Br$ requires C=32·58; H=2·26 per cent.).

Potassium benzene-o-disulphonate.

The preparation of benzene-*o*-disulphonic acid was first attempted from metanilic acid according to the method of Limpricht (*Ber.*, 1876, 9, 553). It was found that the separation of aniline-2 : 3-disulphonic acid from the 2 : 4-disulphonic acid is a very tedious process and the yield and purity of the substance obtained by this method was far from satisfactory. So, after working on this method for a considerable length of time, it had to be

¹ It was insoluble in all ordinary organic solvents, but soluble in caustic alkalis from which it was reprecipitated by acids as a red amorphous powder.

abandoned. The melting point of benzene-*o*-disulphochloride as obtained by Limpricht is given as 105°, but the disulphochloride described in the present paper and prepared according to the method of Armstrong and Napper melts at 143-144°. Evidently Limpricht's benzene-*o*-disulphochloride was impure and probably admixed with some *p*-disulphochloride due to imperfect separation of the parent disulphonic acids.

Twenty-five grams of 1-bromobenzene-3 : 4-potassium disulphonate were heated with 10 gms. of caustic potash, 8 gms. of zinc dust and 800 c.c. of water for 9 to 10 hours. The remaining zinc was filtered off, the solution was saturated with carbonic anhydride and the precipitated zinc carbonate filtered off. The solution on concentration gave crystals which were filtered off, dried and recrystallised from water. The yield was quantitative.

Benzene-o disulphochloride.

Thirteen grams of the sulphochloride were obtained from 20 gms. of potassium-benzene-*o*-disulphonate and 45 gms. of phosphorus pentachloride. It was crystallised from benzene. M. p. 143°.

Reduction of the above Sulphochloride : Formation of Dithiocatechol.

Ten gms. of the benzene-disulphonyl chloride were gradually added to a boiling mixture of 30 gms. of tin and excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid with constant shaking. Here also after 3 to 4 hours a red lump separated which after grinding and further boiling with the reducing agents disappeared, and an oil was formed (which, on exposure to the air at ordinary temperature, was slowly transformed into a red powder).

The oil was distilled with steam and the distillate collected in a receiver cooled in ice where the oil solidified

and acquired a reddish tint. It was rapidly filtered off, dissolved in ice-cold alcohol and reprecipitated by the addition of ice-cold water. It was then kept in a vacuum desiccator where it melted to an oil again. The oil was finally purified by distillation. It boils at 238-239° and solidifies at 28-29°. (Found : S=45.63. $C_6H_4S_2$ requires S=45.77 per cent.)

Fusion of Sodium Thiophenate with Sulphur : Isolation of Dithiocatechol.

Twenty grams of perfectly dry sodium thiophenate were thoroughly mixed with 7 gms. of sulphur and the mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 170° to 180° for six hours. The fused mass was then treated with an excess of dilute sulphuric acid, when there was a profuse evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen and at the same time a dark brown oil of very unpleasant odour separated. The oil was subjected to steam distillation. A portion of the oil distilled over with steam while the greater part, being non-volatile, remained in the distilling vessel. The portion, that was volatile with steam, was found to be unconverted thiophenol.

The residual oil was extracted with ether. It was partly soluble in alkali but insoluble in acid. On allowing it to stand over-night in a vacuum desiccator it turned into a semi-solid mass, which was boiled under reflux with tin and hydrochloric acid for 10 hours and was then extracted with ether. The ether was evaporated off; the residual oil in alcoholic solution gave a yellow lead mercaptide with lead acetate. This in alcoholic suspension was treated with sulphuretted hydrogen when it decomposed giving black lead sulphide, which was separated by filtration. The alcohol was distilled off and the residual oil distilled fractionally; the portion boiling between 233° and 238° (about 5 gms.) was

redistilled, this time the fraction coming over between 238° and 239° was collected. The yield of the pure product was only 1.2 gms. The oil solidifies at 28-29° and is identical with the sample of dithiocatechol prepared by other methods.

Oxidation of Dithiocatechol to its Disulphide.

To an alcoholic solution of the dithiocatechol alcoholic iodine was added in slight excess with shaking when a voluminous yellowish precipitate separated. The precipitate was filtered off and washed with alcohol, potassium iodide solution and finally water. It could not be further purified as it was insoluble in ordinary organic solvents. It melts at 185-190°. (Found: C=51.16; H=3.2. $C_8H_4S_2$ requires C=51.43; H=2.85 per cent.)

Dibenzoyldithiocatechol.

A caustic potash solution of 1 gm. of dithiocatechol was shaken with the calculated quantity of benzoyl chloride, when a solid substance separated out which was filtered off, washed with caustic potash solution and water, and crystallised from acetone. It melts at 77°. (Found: S=17.92. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires S=18.28 per cent.)

o-Nitrobenzylidenedithiocatechol.

A mixture of 1 gm. of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, dithiocatechol and 25 c.c. of alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride was heated in a sealed tube at 100° for 8 hours. After opening the tube the liquid was decanted from the pasty mass, which was then shaken with cold alcohol when shining crystals separated out. The crystalline product was filtered off, washed with cold alcohol and recrystallised from hot alcohol in shining yellow needles. It melts at 106°. (Found: N=5.2. $C_{13}H_9O_2NS_2$ requires N=5.09 per cent.)

Reaction with Acenaphthaquinone.

One gm. of dithiocatechol and 5 gms. of acenaphthaquinone were heated together in an alcoholic solution under reflux for 7-8 hours. The solution was filtered hot and yellow needles separated out from the solution on cooling. The product was recrystallised from alcohol. M. p. 190°. (Found: S=20·4. $C_{18}H_{10}OS_2$ requires S=20·9 per cent.)

Oxidation of Bromo-dithiocatechol: Formation of the Sulphide.

To an alcoholic solution of bromo-dithiocatechol alcoholic iodine solution was added in slight excess when a voluminous precipitate was formed. It was filtered off, washed with alcohol and potassium iodide solution and finally with water. It was insoluble in most organic solvents. It melts at 154°. (Found: C=32·58; H=2·1. $C_8H_3S_2Br$ requires C=32·87; H=1·37 per cent.)

Dibenzoyl-bromodithiocatechol was prepared in the same way as the benzoyl derivative of dithiocatechol. It melts at 85°. (Found: S=14·4. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2BrS_2$ requires S=14·91 per cent.)

Bromodithiocatechol Diethyl Ether.

The potassium salt of 1-bromo-3:4-dithiocatechol (1·5 gms.) was dissolved in 50 per cent. spirit and ethyl bromide was gradually added to it with constant shaking, and the mixture warmed on the water-bath. A crystalline product was obtained from the solution on concentration and cooling which was recrystallised from weak spirit; m. p. 54°. (Found: C=42·99; H=5·1. $C_{10}H_{13}S_2Br$ requires C=43·3; H=4·7 per cent.)

Reaction with Chlorocarbonic Ester : Formation of the Diethylether.

One molecular proportion of the potassium salt of 1-bromo-3:4-dithiocatechol was suspended in dry benzene, and two mols. of chlorocarbonic ester were added to it. The product was then heated for half an hour under reflux when CO_2 evolved. Potassium chloride was filtered off from the hot solution from which shining crystals were obtained on concentration and cooling. The compound was recrystallised from weak spirit. It melts at 54° . (Found: $\text{C}=43.5$; $\text{H}=5.2$. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{S}_2\text{Br}$ requires $\text{C}=43.3$; $\text{H}=4.7$ per cent.)

Reaction with Potassium Monochloracetate : Formation of 1-Bromobenzene-3 : 4-dithio-diglycollic Acid.

To an aqueous solution of 1.5 gms. of the potassium salt of bromodithiocatechol, 2 gms. of monochloracetic acid dissolved in potassium carbonate solution were added and slightly warmed. An amorphous precipitate was obtained from the solution on acidification. This was crystallised from water in shining white plates. The product dissolves in sodium carbonate liberating carbon dioxide. It melts at 170° . (Found: $\text{C}=35.23$; $\text{H}=3.1$. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{S}_2\text{Br}$ requires $\text{C}=35.6$; $\text{H}=2.6$ per cent.)

Reaction with free Monochloracetic Acid : Formation of the Thiolactone (vide p. 322).

An aqueous solution of 1.5 gms. of the K-salt of bromo-dithiocatechol and 3 gms. of monochloracetic acid were boiled for about half an hour. The solution was then cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid, when a white precipitate was obtained which crystallised from water with 2 molecules of water of crystallisation. It is soluble in caustic alkali, but does not liberate

carbon dioxide from sodium bicarbonate. It melts at 191°. (Found: C=32.5; H=3.81. $C_8H_5OS_2Br, 2H_2O$ requires C=32.32; H=3.0 per cent.)

Reaction with Benzalchloride : Formation of Benzylidene-bromodithiocatechol.

The method of preparation is exactly the same as for the following compound. It melts at 170°. (Found: C=50.1; H=3.51. $C_{13}H_{10}S_2Br$ requires C=50.32; H=2.91 per cent.)

Reaction with Acetylenetetrabromide : Formation of Glyoxal-dibromo-dithiocatechol.

The potassium salt of 1-bromo-dithiocatechol (1.5 gms.) and 2 gms. of acetylene tetrabromide were heated under reflux in toluene solution for 1 hour. The separated potassium chloride was filtered off. The solution gave an amorphous solid on dilution with petrol ether. It was crystallised from benzene in prisms. It is insoluble in alcohol and melts at 236-238°. (Found: S=26.89. $C_{14}H_8S_4Br_2$ requires S=27.59 per cent.)

Benzylidene bromo-dithiocatechol from Benzaldehyde and Bromodithiocatechol.

Molecular proportions of bromo-dithiocatechol and benzaldehyde dissolved in alcoholic HCl were heated in a sealed tube at 100° for 7-8 hours. The tube was then opened and the separated solid was filtered off, washed with alcohol and crystallised from benzene. M. p. 169-170°. Mixed m. p. with the product from benzal chloride 169-170°.

Reaction with Thionyl Chloride.

The potassium mercaptide (1.5 gms.) was gradually added to a toluene solution of 1.5 gms. of thionyl chloride, when a violent reaction ensued with the separation

of a yellowish white solid substance. The mixture was then heated under reflux for half an hour. The solid residue obtained on filtration was freed from KCl by washing with water and repeatedly washed with alcohol, and toluene. It was insoluble in all the common organic solvents, hence, it could not be crystallised. It melts with decomposition at 220° (Found: C=27.3; H=1.80. $C_6H_5OBrS_2$ requires C=26.96; H=1.12 per cent.)

Oxalo-bromodithiocatechol.

From 1.5 gms. of the potassium-dimercaptide and 0.5 gm. of oxalyl chloride 0.6 gm. of the oxalo compound was obtained. It was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and benzene. The white crystalline product sublimes at 150° (Found: C=34.61; H=1.46. $C_8H_8O_2BrS_2$ requires C=34.91; H=1.08 per cent.)

Bromodithiocatechol Thiocarbonate.

The potassium mercaptide (1.5 gms.) and thiophosgene (1 gm.) were mixed together in toluene solution and heated under reflux for one hour and a half. The separated potassium chloride was removed by filtration. A reddish yellow precipitate was obtained from the filtrate when alcohol was added to it. It was boiled with bone-charcoal in acetone solution for about half an hour and filtered hot. The filtrate on concentration gave beautiful shining yellow needles, m. p. 140° . (Found: C=31.51; H=1.61. $C_7H_5BrS_4$ requires C=31.51; H=1.14 per cent.)

Reaction with Phthalic Anhydride.

A mixture of bromodithiocatechol and phthalic anhydride in molecular proportions was heated with fused zinc chloride at 125° to 136° for 3-4 hours. The product was then powdered and boiled with a large quantity of

water when a clear solution was obtained which was filtered hot. The filtrate gave shining needle-shaped crystals on cooling, which were recrystallised from water. The compound was insoluble in cold alkali and gave no precipitate with lead acetate. It is easily hydrolysed by acetic acid regenerating the mercaptan. (Found: S=17.9. $C_{14}H_7O_2S_2Br$ requires S=18.2 per cent.)

Phenanthraquinone Monomercaptol.

A mixture of 2 gms. of bromodithiocatechol and 1 gm. of phenanthraquinone was heated in alcoholic solution under reflux for 6 hours. The colour of the solution gradually disappeared and the whole set to a solid mass, which after filtration at the pump was crystallised from boiling acetic acid as a pale yellow crystalline powder. It melts at 195°. (Found: S=14.92. $C_{20}H_{11}OBrS_2$ requires S=15.57 per cent.)

Phenanthraquinone Dimercaptol.

One part of phenanthraquinone and two parts of bromodithiocatechol were heated in a sealed tube in presence of alcoholic HCl at 100° for 7-8 hours. The contents of the tube were filtered, concentrated and cooled, when a white crystalline product was obtained which was recrystallised from hot alcohol. It melts at 115°. (Found: S=20.1. $C_{20}H_{14}Br_2S_4$ requires S=20.8 per cent.)

This work is being continued.

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